

ISic0807

I.Sicily inscription 0807

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Date of discovery and exact provenance not known

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12333

Physical Description

A large slab of the local stone, broken in half (the two halves join)

Dimensions

Height 277 cm

Width 41.5-43 cm

Depth 19.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60 mm

Line 2: 47-60 mm

Line 3: 50-62 mm

Line 4: 55-68 mm

Line 5: 60-64 mm

Line 6: 60 mm

Line 8: 67-70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Σέξτου
2. Πομπηίου
3. Ἄπρου
4. Παλάκου
5. Πομπείας
6. []ϙ[]του
7. [---]
8. Παλάκου

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara

Libertini: ΠΟΜΠΗΙΑ

Libertini: [ΣΕΞΤΟΥ]; Kaibel: ΣΕ[Ξ]ΤΙΟΥ (?)

Translation

Commentary

The two fragments were originally treated as separate inscriptions (and published separately in IG), but Manni Piraino correctly identified that they are part of the same stone.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492826

EDCS 39101586

PHI 140706

PHI 140707

PHI 334831

Bibliography

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